

ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES USING THE SUBSTRUCTURE TECHNIQUE

E. Larrodé*, J.J. Alba*, P. Bravo*, P. Antequera**

** Department of Mechanical Engineering - ICMA
University of Zaragoza - CSIC*

María de Luna, 3, 50015 Zaragoza, Spain

*** Centro Técnico de Aplicaciones*

Vetrotex Spain

Ctra. Nal. II, Alcala de Henares, Madrid, Spain

ABSTRACT

An effective way to analyze structures made of composite materials is presented in this paper. Use of substructures reduces number of degrees of freedom which must be used to define correctly the behaviour of the global structure, gaining computing and modelling time savings. The substructure technique it is usually used on certain occasions when a part of full model is often repeated, substructures libraries can be created then. Concluding, the substructure technique in finite element analysis has been found as an effective method to compute large structures, especially applicable to these with a great number of variables as composite materials structures.

Keywords: composite materials, substructures, finite element method.

1. INTRODUCTION.

In order to cover a wide range of engineering systems the finite element method is frequently used to perform numerical analysis of real systems transforming continuum systems in discrete ones. The approach to reality depends on the grade of discretization made in the system, therefore an intensive discretization of the model (structure) will give us a very good correlation between the behaviour of the numerical model and the real model. In some systems a coarse approach may be sufficient to have an approximate idea about the response, but there are other systems which must be analyzed with care, and even with a fine discretization it is very difficult to obtain good responses by means the numerical model. Then, a very refined modelization is desirable for those zones that are feasible to show unknown behaviour or where the concentration of several factors makes difficult to understand. Substructuring technique solves some problems that due to its complexity or size it is necessary a high number of elements to obtain a solution without a high increase of the number of variables.

2. SOME IMPORTANT PROBLEMS DURING THE ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS STRUCTURES

During the analysis of composite materials structures, some specific problems that due to its complexity need to be analyzed in detail, can be managed using substructuring technique. This

technique allows us to isolate detailed zones or simplify the study in order to reduce solution times and computer storage space. Some of these problems (and some examples) can be grouped as:

- * Reduction of problem size: when size of the problem is very high and it is necessary to reduce the number of variables because time solution and storage requirements. (i.e., layer by layer analysis, repetitive analysis)
- * Detailed studies: a specific part of the model needs to be analyzed in detail and a refined meshing increase the number of variables. (i.e. joints, holes, free edge, crack growth, delamination)
- * Double behaviour: due to long time solutions, linear and nonlinear parts must be isolated in order to reduce time computing. (i.e. local buckling, interface contact analysis, dynamic analysis)
- * Subdivided analysis: when a structure is composed by an amount of parts and these parts could be being designed at different stages or by several persons or some of these are considered as variables and others as constants or even because of the size of the problem . (i.e., assembled structures, multilevel systems)

3. THEORETICAL PROCEDURE.

Substructuring is the procedure which consists of the division of a single structure into several component substructures. One of the goals to employ the substructure technique is when a large structure has to be calculated and it is necessary to obtain a complete and detailed information about the response under different loads. If the structure has been generated with a large number of finite elements to get the purpose above mentioned, then a substructure technique can be used in order not to exceed the available computer capacity. In this case a substructure technique is feasible to be used due to the great number of variables of the problem. The general procedure can be summarized as follows; firstly the part which has been selected to be repeated along the complete model can be modeled as usual and a set of master degrees of freedom must be saved. Secondly the substructure matrices are calculated and written in a file. Once the substructure has been formulated, it may be used in the same way as others standards finite elements. Several advantages can be achieved if this technique is used, but commonly are used to separate some parts of the model from the rest of the structure or when a structure can be idealized as a repetition of a single substructure. Some of these advantages can be summarized as follows:

- * Substructuring can be used as an efficient optimization tool. When the design needs to preserve certain component to be unvaried, these parts can be modeled as substructures and therefore isolated from the rest of the structure, then during the analysis remain unchanged by redesign or mesh refinement applied to the rest of the model.
- * The work can be subdivided between several designers and modeled independently, joining different parts to construct the complete model.
- * Others important advantages are modeling and solution time savings for a structure having repeated or symmetric parts. Therefore, one of this parts can be formed as a substructure which can be repeated to form the entire structure.
- * Time saving during the calculation can be achieved not only by means the use of repeated substructures but by the ability to separate the stresses from displacements calculation.
- * Once the substructure has been modeled and formulated different types of analyses can be performed in the same substructure without having to form and re-triangularize the stiffness matrix.

* A separation between linear and non linear parts of the structure can be done, so it is not necessary that linear parts of the model are subjected to an iterative solution simplifying the analysis this way.

The basis of this technique involves matrix condensation, so the stiffness matrix and the mass matrix are reduced to a group of master degrees of freedom. These sets of master degrees of freedom must be selected carefully because they have the role to define correctly or as approximate as it is possible the working of the structure which is being analyzed. A brief description of the procedure of condensation and recovery is presented. Consider the part B of the structure in figure (3.1.) which has been taken as a substructure. For this substructure the equilibrium equations can be written in matrix form.

$$[K] \{\phi\} = \{F\} \quad (1)$$

where:

$[K]$ = symmetric stiffness matrix

$\{\phi\}$ = displacement vector

$\{F\}$ = external force vector

Figure 3.1. Example of condensation process.

Substructure B is composed by inner nodes (i) and boundary ones (b) or nodes which are connecting the substructure B with the rest of the structure, then equation (1) can be rewritten in partitioned form as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} [K_{ii}] & [K_{ib}] \\ [K_{bi}] & [K_{bb}] \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} \{\phi_i\} \\ \{\phi_b\} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \{F_i\} \\ \{F_b\} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where:

$$[K_{ii}] \{\phi_i\} + [K_{ib}] \{\phi_b\} = \{F_i\} \quad (3)$$

$$[K_{bi}] \{\phi_i\} + [K_{bb}] \{\phi_b\} = \{F_b\} \quad (4)$$

where $\{\phi_b\}$ are boundary degrees of freedom to be retained and $\{\phi_i\}$ are degrees of freedom to be eliminated. Elimination of internal degrees of freedom $\{\phi_i\}$ gives a condensed equation, then from (3) we have:

$$\{\phi_i\} = [K_{ii}]^{-1} \{F_i\} - [K_{ii}]^{-1} [K_{ib}] \{\phi_b\} \quad (5)$$

and substituting (5) in (4)

$$\{F_b\} - [K_{bi}] [K_{ii}]^{-1} \{F_i\} = ([K_{bb}] - [K_{bi}] [K_{ii}]^{-1} [K_{ib}]) \{\phi_b\} \quad (6)$$

defining two new matrices $[\tilde{K}_b]$ and $\{\tilde{F}_b\}$ as:

$$[\tilde{K}_b] = [K_{bb}] - [K_{bi}] [K_{ii}]^{-1} [K_{ib}] \quad (7)$$

$$\{\tilde{F}_b\} = \{F_b\} - [K_{bi}] [K_{ii}]^{-1} \{F_i\} \quad (8)$$

then (6) changes to:

$$\{\tilde{F}_b\} = [\tilde{K}_b] \{\phi_b\} \quad (9)$$

with this expression we are able to define a new transformation which relate a new loads vector ($\{\tilde{F}_b\}$, the condensed loads vector) with the displacements of the boundary nodes ($\{\phi_b\}$), being $[\tilde{K}_b]$ the condensed stiffness matrix which relate them.

In the same way, it can be found similar expressions for the substructures A and C and successively it can be feasible to establish the equilibrium equations in matrix form, in the common boundaries of the three substructures. The assembly operation with substructures can be done like standard finite elements to calculate the displacements in the degrees of freedom of the common boundary nodes. This set of assembled substructures generate the main structure which is defined by the degrees of freedom belonging to the common boundary nodes plus those which do not belong to the condensed part of the structure if they exist. Then the equilibrium equations can be written as:

$$\{\tilde{F}_b\}^A \{\tilde{F}_b\}^B \{\tilde{F}_b\}^C = \{F_b\}^T \quad (10)$$

where $\{F_b\}^T$ is the external loads vector acting in common boundaries of the three substructures. Once the total structure has been calculated the displacements in the inner nodes of the different substructures can be recovered and following an inverse method the internal displacements can be obtained. Bearing in mind equation (2) for each substructure, we can express the equation for each substructure affected by the others substructures as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} [K_{ii}] & [K_{ib}] \\ [K_{bi}] & [K_{bb}] \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} \{\Phi_i\} \\ \{\Phi_b\} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \{F_i\} \\ \{F_b\}^T \end{Bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

$\{F_b\}^T$ can be obtained adding the external loads on the boundary nodes of the substructure plus the actions transferred by the others substructures in these nodes.

Solving equation (11):

$$\{\Phi_i\} = [K_{ii}]^{-1} \{F_i\} - [K_{ii}]^{-1} [K_{ib}] \{\Phi_b\} \quad (12)$$

Remembering the expression of displacements of inner nodes in (5):

$$\{\phi_i\} = [K_{ii}]^{-1} \{F_i\} - [K_{ii}]^{-1} [K_{ib}] \{\phi_b\} \quad (13)$$

we can obtain $[K_{ii}]^{-1} \{F_i\}$ from (13):

$$[K_{ii}]^{-1} \{F_i\} = \{\phi_i\} + [K_{ii}]^{-1} [K_{ib}] \{\phi_b\} \quad (14)$$

Now we need to know the boundary displacements vector for each substructure $\{\phi_b\}$.

By means a unit load applied to boundary degrees of freedom the calculation of $[\tilde{K}_b]$ can be done, applying this load to the equations obtained in the condensation phase for each substructure:

$$\begin{bmatrix} [\mathbf{K}_{ii}] & [\mathbf{K}_{ib}] \\ [\mathbf{K}_{bi}] & [\mathbf{K}_{bb}] \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} \{\phi'_i\} \\ \{\phi'_b\} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \{0\} \\ \{1\} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

solving this system:

$$\{\phi'_i\} = -[\mathbf{K}_{ii}]^{-1} [\mathbf{K}_{ib}] \{\phi'_b\} \quad (16)$$

$$([\mathbf{K}_{bb}] - [\mathbf{K}_{bi}] [\mathbf{K}_{ii}]^{-1} [\mathbf{K}_{ib}]) \{\phi'_b\} = \{1\} \quad (17)$$

then, as in (7) we obtain:

$$[\tilde{\mathbf{K}}_b] = \{\phi'_b\}^{-1} \quad (18)$$

Now as in equation (9):

$$\{\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_b\} = \{\phi'_b\}^{-1} \{\phi_b\} \Rightarrow \{\phi_b\} = \{\phi'_b\} \{\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_b\} \quad (19)$$

Then substituting in equation (14):

$$[\mathbf{K}_{ii}]^{-1} \{\mathbf{F}_i\} = \{\phi_i\} + [\mathbf{K}_{ii}]^{-1} [\mathbf{K}_{ib}] \{\phi'_b\} \{\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_b\} \quad (20)$$

and applying equation (16):

$$[\mathbf{K}_{ii}]^{-1} \{\mathbf{F}_i\} = \{\phi_i\} - \{\phi'_i\} \{\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_b\} \quad (21)$$

Finally returning to equation (12) we have:

$$\{\Phi_i\} = \{\phi_i\} - \{\phi'_i\} \{\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_b\} - [\mathbf{K}_{ii}]^{-1} [\mathbf{K}_{ib}] \{\Phi_b\} \quad (22)$$

where all in the above formula are known.

The condensation process increase its own difficulty when substructures are modeled with other substructures, in this case substructure equations are gradually condensed until all internal degrees of freedom in the substructure are eliminated. Then a branch system can be created in order to organize the inputs and outputs of design variables in a model.

4. APPLICATION TO LAMINATED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

About the matter we are dealing to, an important benefit of the substructure technique can be obtained, bearing in mind we are working with laminated composite materials exists an entity which is repeated along the whole structure, the sublaminates. A reasonable decision may be to modelize sublaminates as substructures, and then the laminate can be constructed in easy form; number of plies, orientation of each lamina as well as the material which is made, are then matter of the substructure (see figure 4.1.). A library of sublaminates (substructures) can be created and in order to make easy the selection of the sublaminates during the optimization phase, can be ordered and classified. An effective method to obtain computing and modelling time savings can be achieved using libraries of substructures which correspond to certain sublaminates.

Figure 4.1. Structuring of laminates.

The substructure can be modeled and model meshes may be done as usual in a finite element analysis, each lamina can be modeled with finite elements, then a first analysis determines nodal loads and stiffness for nodes on boundaries. These nodes are the master nodes which join a substructure with others, and depending on the degrees of freedom have been selected and the type of analysis, the approach may vary from a rude approximation (selecting a few degrees of freedom) to the exact response (selecting all nodes with all its degrees of freedom). In figure 4.2. an example of laminate meshing can be seen, the laminate generated with solid elements is transformed in a substructure where nodes are on interface boundaries (condensation procedure).

Figure 4.2. Mesh generation in laminates.

Once the sublaminates has been constructed as a substructure, node displacements on the interface boundaries are calculated by solving the equations of the system. When node displacements are obtained, interface degrees of freedom of a sublaminates (substructure) are recovered and used to analyze this sublaminates under both these degrees of freedom recovered (boundary d.o.f.) and known loads in internal degrees of freedom (recovery procedure).

Figure 4.3. Example of laminate grouping to optimize computing time.

So, depending on the type of laminate stacking we can construct different grouping in order to have an optimum number of plies per substructure. As an example, a number of six plies per substructure were found during the analysis of a structure composed by laminated plates (Figure 4.3. and 4.4).

Figure 4.4. Optimum number of plies per substructure

During the calculation of the entire model an important drawback to the use of substructuring can be found due to the stiffness matrix of a substructure is a full matrix, and so may be large if the substructure has a large number of condensed degrees of freedom. This may mean an increase of the wavefront of the model leading to long computer times to solve the equations. Then, it is necessary to find the appropriate number of boundary nodes and its corresponding degrees of freedom by careful choice, moreover several substructures are used rather than a single larger substructure. An optimum number of substructures could be found which avoided this difficulty as can be seen in figure 4.5.

Figure 4.5. Optimum number of substructures per substructure in a model.

5. DESIGNING COMPOSITE MATERIALS STRUCTURES

5.1. Design procedure.

The design of structures made of composite materials is done taking into account a large number of factors which make the process more complicated due to increasing of number of variables. Now, the stacking sequence of laminates, different orientation layers, types of joints (adhesived, bolted, ...), etc. make increase the number of variables of the problem greatly. Therefore a powerful tool to manage the whole of variables of the design is recommended. So, the finite element method it is usually selected to carry on this task, moreover workstations provide the possibility to solve the problem in a short period of time. Important advantages can be achieved if the substructure technique is used in large composite materials structures because of the methodology of this technique it is based in the subdivision of the work, and when a high number of variables is used and a routine of optimization is suitable to be implemented, the benefits which can be obtained are considerable. Large structures can be successfully analyzed by subdividing it in levels which may represent each one parts which consist in.

Several uses of substructuring have been applied in the designing of all types of structures which are presented in this paper. Repeated parts of the design have been modeled as a sequence of patterns which have been modeled as substructures, so, in the model, different types of substructures have been modeled, from structural parts of the structure to sublaminates in the panels which the structure can be composed. In some occasions have been necessary to obtain the information of particular areas of special interest in detailed form because they are critical points of the design such a joints, holes, edges etc. and must be analyzed with care. Other parts of the design which were considered as fixed component because of their design or manufacture and could not be allowed to vary during the calculation, were isolated from the rest of the structure, remaining unchanged by redesign or mesh refinement changes applied to the rest of the structure. A multilevel system can be used to analyze the whole design. Several parts of the design can be considered as substructures due to have the possibility to be optimized during the analysis, so it is easier to change the type of substructure than to re-modelize the entire model. However, other parts of the model can be modeled as substructures because of their complicate and unknown way of working. Different parts of the model may be modeled by several designers, therefore computing and modeling time savings can be obtained, getting this way an effective method to work.

Depending on the type of structure different analysis can be carried out, so, some structures are feasible to be analyzed with determined types of elements of which formulation is easier than others. The type of element which is going to be used it is very important because involve several factors as number of degrees of freedom, necessary numbers of points to define correctly behaviour of the structure, its formulation, etc. We can distinguish among beam systems (with beam elements), surface systems (involving shell, plates, axisymmetric elements), and solid systems (solid elements).

5.2. Analysis of structures.

Simple models for each substructure can be modeled prior to definitive modelization in order to know its behaviour and to control CPU time used and computer storage requirements. An initial simple analysis of the whole model give us an idea of the behaviour of the model as well as critical areas of the design. Once initial analysis is finished next step consists of the model subdivision in substructures, each one representing parts of the structure. Component of the main structure can be analyzed separately and optimized according to general requirements of the design, later, each part it is brought together to form the full model. Important aspects during the modelization are node locations and elements connectivity among different substructures, so a careful selection of nodes which join substructures each other is used in order to avoid discontinuities. A continuous communication between people who modelize different substructures must be established, so information about the position of boundary nodes is taken at each stage during modelization. When using substructures, degrees of freedom of a substructure it is a decisive parameter which give us an idea about the approach that we are intended to have. When analyzing some structures there are basically two possibilities to find the situation of boundary nodes (Figure 5.2.1.). Determined (or fixed) boundary nodes and non-determined (non-fixed) boundary nodes, are influenced by the type of connection zone among substructures. Determined boundaries (Type I) are those which there is no doubt to select the appropriate number of boundary degrees of freedom, because the separation stripe among two substructures it is very short, and number of degrees of freedom do not increase greatly the number of variables of the problem. In case of undetermined boundaries (Type II) a selection of main degrees of freedom is feasible to be done in order to decrease number of variables.

Figure 5.2.1. Types of boundary connections.

A library can be created during the modelization process. A mesh refinement can be done in some parts of the structures because of their working. Once the full model is constructed an exhaustive analysis of the whole model is carried out and the first results are obtained, then, these results must be returned to different substructures and suitable modifications may be made on each one. An iterative process of optimization is then established until the principal purposes are achieved. Once the iterative process is ended the results provided by the analysis are compared with experimental testing, and an optimum design of the structure is obtained. Information about working of structural component of structures is studied separately. Referring to the entire model, number of modules as well as situation in the main structure can also be analyzed. Notice that every change in a part of the structure affects the other ones, so decisions must be carefully done, this is why an analysis of the entire model in each step during the calculation process it is very helpful.

5.3. Substructuring work scheme and general procedure.

A detailed workplan concerning of design, modelization, optimization, calculation, verification, etc. which involve several persons can be made carefully. As a result, an efficient process to analyze large structures in composite materials may be developed, and not only an amount of conclusions about the working of the structure and the behaviour of the composite materials which are used but the work scheme, the problems which may be avoided, effective subdivision of the structure and the work time optimization, can be obtained.

Figure 5.3.1. Task Flux-Diagram.

During the preparation of workplans before the analysis of the structure started, several schemes are performed to do the task in an effective form. While the analysis is running some changes are completing the general scheme and certain aspects referring to timetable are feasible to be modified. After work is done punctual conclusions are added to the general diagram. A résumé of the general procedure can be seen in figure 5.3.1. A suggested scheme to generate substructures is presented in figure 5.3.2. This particular procedure to work with substructures it is only intended to show how a substructure can be prepared to share in general calculation calculation process.

Figure 5.3.2. Generation, storage and managing of substructures.

5.4. Classification according to structure working.

At the time to make a study of a system, a general previous classification depending on the reason because substructuring has been selected to carry on this task, can be done. So we can find different groups in which our structure can be included, some of them are summarized in following four.

- 1) Repetitive structures.
- 2) Structures with singularities.
- 3) Double behaviour structures.
 - linear/nonlinear
 - dynamic/static
- 4) Large or assembled structures.

6. NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL TESTING COMPARISON.

Experimental testing have been done most of times in order to prove the validity of results obtained during the numerical calculation. A close correlation between experimental and numerical results have been obtained during the design process. As the approach inherent in the basic formulation of the finite element method and round-off errors in numerical calculation process let us obtain good results, the matrix condensation is not a approximate but exact procedure. Selecting all degrees of freedom from boundary nodes (or connecting nodes among substructures) we obtain the same result as in cases of a complete modelization of the structure (without substructuring). So, by means a careful choice of some relevant nodes as well as determined degrees of freedom, we obtain a good approach to the global response. Depending on the knowledge of the problem, the process to reduce the number of boundary degrees of freedom it can be feasible to be done, whereas in other cases it is impossible to predict. Next table shows some examples where the substructure technique has

been used, depending on the reason why this technique has been used, a classification of different applications has been done.

Table 6.1. Different uses of substructures.

I) Repetitive structures	Laminated plates (1) Electrification towers (2) Bonnet (3) Stiffened sandwiches (4) 3-D sandwich fabric Train wheel
II) Structures with singularities	Variable thickness testing Joints Holes Impact testing Notched beam testing
III) Double behaviour structures	Crushing of tubes (1) Train wheel (2) Local buckling (3)
IV) Large structures, assembled structures and multilevel systems	Mountain bicycle (1) Foundations for posts (2) Bus structure (3) Isotherm self portable trailer (4) Truck frame (5) Structural constructions (6)

In figure 6.1. some examples of different substructuring uses are showed indicating the reason why has been used. In these examples experimental comparison has been done and a good correlation has been found.

7. CONCLUSIONS

Finite element computer codes with the substructure technique has been used to analyze structures made of composite materials. Due to great number of variables involved by the problem the use of this technique simplifies modelization, solution and recovery of results.

As an important advantage of this technique it can be mentioned that a subdivision of the work can be carried out. The principal goals of this subdivision are :

- isolation of critical zones (mesh refinement on detailed studies).
- separation among design variables and constants.
- separation among stresses and displacements calculations.
- separation among linear and nonlinear analysis.
- selective changes can be done in specific substructures without a global remeshing.
- efficient method to store substructures and to create an ease use of libraries.
- branch system with several substructuring levels can be established.
- a work team can be created.

An increment in the number of boundary degrees of freedom implies a higher size of the problem but reliable results are obtained instead. Sometimes several substructures are preferable than a few great substructures in order to avoid long solution times and an excessive computer storage space,

I.1.) Repetitive component examples, and optimum grouping in substructures. Modelling saving.

I.2.) Repetitive structures examples. Storage capacity is improved.

I.3.) Repetitive zones examples in a structure. Computing time saving.

I.4.) Substructures storage examples and use of libraries.

II) Detailed studies examples. A mesh refinement can be done without an excessive increase of the problem using substructures where the singularity is located.

III.1.) Differentiation between design variables and constants. Double behaviour (static and dynamic analysis) is also used.

Figure 6.1. Substructuring uses.

III.2.) Solving time saving obtained in a non linear analysis isolating contact zones (non linear behaviour) with the others.

III.3.) Detailed analysis and double behaviour analysis example. Local buckling of beams.

IV.1.) Determined master nodes example, type I in figure 5.2.1.

IV.2.) Work subdivision example because of the difference between manufacture processes and material behaviour.

IV.3.) Multilevel system example.

IV.4.) Assembled substructures example.

IV.5.) Separation between stresses and displacements calculations due to long solution times.

IV.6.) Large structure example. Storage requirements

Figure 6.1. Substructuring uses (cont.).

then an optimum number of degrees of freedom per substructure and substructures per model can be obtained.

Important modelling and solution time savings can be obtained with this technique. The order of the system matrices is reduced, and the stiffness matrix of only the first element need to be derived this reduces the computer effort required. Large detailed structures can be analyzed in a very short period of time and because of time saving, optimization process and sensibility analysis can be carried out.

An effective method to analyze large structures (by means a small model) can be achieved by making a library of substructures and it is specially recommended in repetitive models avoiding computer storage and CPU time limitations.

References

1. Jones R. M. *Mechanics of composite materials*. Hemisphere Publishing Corporation, 1975.
2. Bathe, K.J. and Wilson, E.L. *Numerical methods in finite element analysis*. Prentice-Hall, 1976
3. ABAQUS, version 4.9, Hibbitt, Karlsson and Sorensen, Inc.
4. Zienkiewicz, O.C. *El método de los elementos finitos*. Ed. Reverté, 1980.
5. Tsai S. W. *Theory of Composite Design*. Think Composites, 1992.
6. Przemieniecki, J.S. *Theory of matrix structural analysis*. Mc Graw-Hill, 1968
7. Mondkar D.P. and Powell G.H. *Large Capacity Equation Solver for Structural Analysis*. Computer and Structures, Vol. 4, 1974, pp. 699-728
8. Oden J.T. and Kikuchi N. *Fifth Invitational Symposium of the Unification of Finite Elements, Finite Differences, Calculus of Variations*. H. Kardestuncer, Editor University of Connecticut at Storrs, 1980
9. Irons, B. and Ahmad, S. *Techniques of finite elements*. Ellis Horwood Ltd., Chichester, England 1980
10. Kim J. Y. and Hong C. S. *Three-Dimensional Finite Element Analysis of Interlaminar Stresses in Thick Composite Materials*. Computers & Structures, Vol. 40, No. 6, pp. 1395-1404, 1991.
11. Liu Xia-shi. *Finite Element Analysis for Large Composite Structure*. Proceedings of ICCS IV, Paisley, Scotland, 1987.